

Influencer Marketing in the Digital Era

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Abstract:

With the rapid growth of Internet usage, the use of digital marketing has increased significantly. Using emails, messages, calls, social media, etc to market a product helps the businesses to tap a market that isn't really possible by using traditional marketing methods due to the physical limitations. Among these digital methods is the method of using the help of influencers. Businesses reach out to these influencers who, then, use and preview the product for their followers. This study aims to observe how these personnel influence their followers with or against the product. There are two types of influencers: Micro and Macro, and it has been observed time and again that micro influencers round up a much more loyal base for the products. Consumers conclude that there is a personal connection with these micro influencers and a factor of trust, compared to the celebrities. Algorithms are trained based on the consumer's behaviours, feeding them more of these influencers to build a compelling urge to buy— mostly impulsively. Trends like Fear of Missing Out observe how impulsively a consumer tends to buy something they see on the Internet — how compulsive it feels.

Keywords: *Digital Marketing. Consumer behaviour. Micro-influencers. Influencer Marketing. Impulse buying.*

Introduction:

With the rapid growth of internet usage, the use of digital resources for marketing has increased significantly. Traditionally, marketing is a big part of a business to bring the product produced or the service rendered to the consumer who needs them, and marketing was used to do the same. Advertisements in local paper, television, pamphlets, etc, were used to promote the product in the hopes of reaching the right audience. As much as it worked, it did only to a certain extent. The time consuming and costly nature of traditional marketing led the world to find alternatives that were essentially cheaper, more efficient, and could reach a larger group of people.

What started with digital advertisements, posters, tweets, has now led to hiring people to

talk good about the products being sold. They were called influencers—a perfectly fitting name for personnel hired to influence one to buy the product in an efficient way. Through the form of either long-form or short-form videos, tweets [on X/Twitter], or other social media platforms, they share their knowledge of the product. It includes their review of the product, the steps to use it properly, and the results that they got from following the process. Watching these influencers praise – most of the times – the product leads to the consumer believing that it could benefit them just as well. It is basic human psychology, which entails the increase in buying of the product the more the content becomes famous.

Influencers are the people with the power to influence someone into buying a product. Listing the qualities of the product at their hands, listing

the process of use, and answering questions asked by the public on the business' behalf. With an influential technique of Word of Mouth, one of the oldest in the book, they spread the word, trying to reach the product to the consumer in need of it. The algorithm, then, having studied the mannerisms of the consumer, suggests content based on past interactions with such influencers.

Objectives:

1. To study the impact of influencers and social media on businesses
2. To study how influencers effect well as opposed to traditional marketing.
3. To study the trust of a consumer in the influencers.

Review of Literature:

- **The Journal of Business Research [2021]** refers to Consumer's reaction to Business' Transformation to Digital Platforms as, "Digital Transformation and resultant business model innovation have fundamentally altered consumers' expectations and behaviours, putting immense pressure on traditional firms, and disrupting numerous markets." They proceed to highlight the three stages of digital transformation— digitisation, digitalisation, and digital transformation.
- Influencer marketing best ties up with **the Source Attractiveness model [McGuire, 1985]**. It has been observed over multiple studies, mostly performed on athletes, that a consumer feels attracted to three aspects of the communication source: likability, similarity, and familiarity. It posits that the endorser's attractiveness enhances the efficiency with which the product is received by the general public.

- **Another study [2024]** explains the role of influencers based on the number of followers they have and influence. They are divided into two classifications, namely Micro [having anywhere from 10,000 to 1,00,000 followers] influencers and Macro [above 1,00,000 followers] influencers. It has been observed that a consumer will trust an influencer with whom they feel a personal connection. With higher numbers, it is harder to achieve that kind of trust, and thus, a product is trusted more if it was marketed by a micro-influencer.

Methodology:

Descriptive and analytical in nature, this research was based on secondary data collected from books, journals, research papers, and industry reports after being checked for reliability. Some of the behavioural research was also conducted on existing social platforms including Instagram and YouTube to analyze how the product is marketed in the actual market.

One of the most important sources in this research was the Journal of Business Research, published in 2021, as it was the primary source for most of the data obtained, observed, and analyzed.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Growth of Influencer Marketing in Digital Marketing:

According to Lou and Yuan [2019], Influencers create content on social media in their areas of specialization, disseminating persuasive messages that combine information and entertainment to promote a brand of product. Consumers are usually driven to such influencers to aid their decision-making process. It has been observed time and again that when an influencer puts forth a product, it is more likely to be sold than by advertisements. We, as humans, are wired to chase what attracts us, and sometimes that is these influencers. They propose arguments which

sit just right, influencing a person into buying the product. The entertainment value of the product causes a big part, and thus there has been seen a growth in influencer marketing.

Impact on Consumer Trust:

Compared to the traditional means of marketing such as email campaigns, or advertisements, influencer marketing offers a more personal connection with the consumer. It has been studied that this personal connection formed between the influencers and the consumers works in goodwill for the business concern, bringing in more traffic. Moreover, it has been observed that the businesses making the use of micro- and nano-influencers round up a more loyal group of consumers. The celebrity influencers are influential, yes, but they aren't as trustworthy. A mere consumer does not have the need to know if a certain top tier celebrity was paid a larger sum to say the words, and thus, is harder to trust.

Purchase Intention & Impulse buying:

Several scholars have observed that the repeated exposure of a consumer to these influences leads to an intention of creating a purchase. An algorithm is trained on the very same principle. To show a person more of what they want, to expose them to these products multiple times creates a plan of purchase. A trend like FOMO, or Fear Of Missing Out, is the perfect example highlighting the humane need of wanting something you see the person in front of you have. It is not irrational for it is most normal, and yet more profitable for a business. Such a trend leads to persons impulsively spending their money to purchase these products, bringing in more business.

Findings:

- Influencers tend to sell the product more than traditional marketing.
- Nano- and Micro-influencers create a more loyal market for the product than celebrities.
- Consumers tend to trust smaller influencers as they feel there is more of a connection.
- Trends like Fear of Missing Out lead to impulse buying.
- An algorithm is trained to feed the consumer what the businesses want.

Conclusion:

The study examined the role of influencers in this new world of digital marketing and how it has changed the market for better or for worse. It observed how the consumers tend to react to certain trends, how the buying mentality is created. Algorithms are trained based on the behaviours of the consumers— what is liked and purchased, while what is discarded.

Recommendations:

1. Choose the Right type of Influencer:
2. Brands should prioritise working with micro-influencers, because there is a chance of higher engagement there. It is suitable to pick niche creators whose audience matches the product being marketed.
3. Prioritise Authentic content:
4. Instead of plagiarising content from other brands, or creating something cheap and not-useful, it is always preferred to make authentic content that fits the brand and can be called their own.
5. Ensure Transparency:
6. Transparency is the practice of not hiding the company policies from the influencers promoting the product, and in turn, the consumer. If a brand is more transparent, there is a higher trust factor.

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